

Increased reliability of tidal turbines thanks to a better knowledge of realistic tidal conditions, use of RAM analysis, advanced monitoring, maintenance strategies and intelligent design components.

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Abstract – The present paper presents the Reliability, Availability and Maintainability analysis performed by the authors in the framework of the H2020 REALTIDE project on two tidal turbine concepts - “complex bottom fixed tidal turbine” and “floating multirotor tidal turbine” (herewith called concept 1 and concept 3 respectively). The objective was to assess their designs and conditioning monitoring to enhance their reliability and availability performances. The two concepts were modelled by means of Monte-Carlo based software in order to study the impact of their failures to operational availability, and to determine the most critical components to unavailability. The study calculated an availability of 72.8% for concept 1 and 80.1% for concept 3; and the most critical components were similar for both concepts: Gearbox and High-Speed Shaft, Power Electronic Converter, Pitch System, Yaw system, Control System, Blade, and Generator. In both cases, several design modifications and monitoring were proposed and simulated in alternatives cases. The alternative case defined to maximise the turbine availability proposes a full set of implementations as the simplification of the tidal turbine design, redundancy of the Power Electronic Converter and Control System, and monitoring of Blades and Generator. The resulting availability of the tidal turbine is increased by +14.21% (concept 1) and +9.30% (concept 3) comparing with the base cases. The influence of the weather and maintenance logistics were simulated in sensitivity cases and will be also presented in this paper.

Keywords – Tidal Turbine, RAM analysis, Reliability, Maintenance strategy, Condition Monitoring, Design optimization.

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I. INTRODUCTION

At present, there is a great energy demand in the whole planet. This demand has led to important technological advances in all branches of the energy sector in recent decades and a huge boom in renewable energy. This boom has led to the study and research of new methods for the extraction of energy through natural resources, promoting alternatives such as tidal energy technology.

Tidal stream power technology has gained prominence because of: its similarity with wind turbines; the ability to harvest energy directly from tidal currents which are a perfectly predicible phenomenon and inexhaustible; and the potentially non-intrusive nature of the system. Obviously, this emergent technology is all under development and consequently there is no bank of information about their operating reliability.

There are three important factors that limit the development of maintenance and monitoring plans for tidal turbines:

- The fact that this technology is at an early development threshold makes it necessary to use data from the accumulated experience in similar technologies such as wind turbines [1];
- Small number of research and development of different types of Tidal Turbines (horizontal axis, vertical axis, floating tethered, seabed fixed, etc.) [2]; and
- The harsh marine environment and problems with accessibility for maintenance [1].

As part of the H2020 REALTIDE project, the authors studied several generic tidal turbine concepts by means of

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a Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) [3]. From this study, a Reliability, Availability and Maintainability (RAM) analyses were performed on two selected concepts for to assess their designs and monitoring performances. The two selected concepts ere a “complex bottom fixed tidal turbine” and a “floating multirotor tidal turbine” (herewith called concept 1 and concept 3 respectively).

For each concept, the RAM analyses took in account their design specifications, equipment reliability and maintainability and operational environment conditions. The two concepts were modelled by means of a Monte-Carlo based RAM software in order to study the impact of their failures on the system performance, i.e., its operational availability. These models were called “base cases” and were used as a reference to compare with the “alternative” and “sensitivity” cases described hereafter. From the base cases, it was also determined the most critical components for each concepts, i.e., those that contribute the most to turbine’s unavailability.

Then, design and monitoring recommendations were proposed on the critical components with the purpose to increase turbine’s performance. Those recommendations were implemented in the “base case” models in order to assess their effectiveness to increase system availability. The models that included these recommendations were called “alternative cases”.

Finally, other simulations, called “sensitivity cases”, were performed to assess the models robustness to data variations and uncertainties.

This paper presents the RAM analysis performed during the RealTide project and its contribution to better understand how advanced monitoring, maintenance strategies and enhanced design component can increase reliability of tidal turbines in realistic tidal conditions.

Sections II and III describe respectively the objective and the scope of the RAM study in the RealTide project. The RAM methodology and modelling approach are explained in section IV. Section V presents how reliability data were selected and obtained for the modelled tidal turbines. Several models (or cases) were performed during the project. Each model is built based on assumptions which are summarized in section VI. Finally the results and conclusion are presented in sections VII and VIII.

II. REALTIDE RAM OBJECTIVES

One of the objectives of RealTide project is to implement RAM analysis on “generic” tidal turbine as part of the solution to assess the design and monitoring performances taking into account the design specifications, equipment reliability and maintainability in its operational environment. With the difficulty to define a “generic” tidal turbine, the authors defined four different generic concepts turbines which would cover most of the concepts existing now a days and were studied in a previous FMEA analysis in RealTide [3]. Two different tidal turbine concepts were selected and modelled by means of Monte-

Carlo based software in order to study the impact of their failures to the system performance, i.e. its operational availability, and determine the most critical components, i.e. those that contribute the most to unavailability. Due to data uncertainties, sensitivity cases were performed in order to assess the model robustness. Design and monitoring recommendations have been proposed and assessed in alternative cases in order to assess their effectiveness to increase system availability.

III. SCOPE OF THE RAM STUDY

The scope of this study covered the main components included in the generic tidal turbine concept 1 (Complex bottom fixed) and concept 3 (Floating multi rotor) presented in the FMEA previously performed in 4 different concepts [3].

The concept 1 – “complex bottom fixed” (Fig. 1) has horizontal axis rotors (i.e. axis of rotation parallel to the flow direction) with 3 blades and are fixed to the seabed via piling. In the complex fixed concept, the blades have pitch control, whereas the nacelle is completed with the yaw mechanism in order to maximize the produced energy. It also has a gearbox to represent indirect drive turbine. The selected type of generator for this concept is DFIG (Doubly-Fed Induction Generator). In order to capture various type of foundation, piling is included in this model. Overall, this model is selected to be analyzed since it is one of the most common model developed by various turbine companies.

Fig. 1. Complex bottom fixed tidal turbine concept - 3D Model

The concept 3 – “Floating multi-rotor concept” (Fig. 2) has a horizontal axis rotor which is connected to two blades. It has pitch control and no active yaw mechanism although the floating structure can rotate around the turret which is moored to the seabed via mooring lines. A gearbox is connected to the drive. The generator type for concept 3 is induction generator.

Fig. 2. Floating multi rotor - 3D Model

IV. RAM METHODOLOGY

A. RAM description

Asset systems are designed to perform a function in order to achieve a minimum production or service level. However assets failures reduce the capability of the system to meet these targets and, at the same time, increase the operational costs. For example, wind turbines are shut down about 24 to 36 hours per year for scheduled maintenance [11], resulting to a theoretical service level of about 99.5%. However, as per [10], wind turbines availability is on average 85% due to equipment breakdown, leading to unexpected loss of production and extra costs. A way to increase assets availability is to increase their reliability by means of an enhanced design.

RAM is one of the most performing tools to assess systems design. Indeed, RAM modelling estimates the performance of a system, which is computed in terms of operational availability or production capabilities. The results from a RAM modelling will identify possible causes of production losses and can examine possible system alternatives. The RAM study is thus a tool for decision-making allowing costs versus benefits analysis.

RAM modelling simulates the configuration, operation, failure, repair and maintenance of all assets included in a system. The inputs for a RAM modelling of a system include the physical components, equipment configuration, Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) and Mean Time To Repair (MTTR), maintenance philosophy & logistics and operational profile. The outputs determine the resulting operational performance of the system over its life cycle.

In the RAM process, the systems to be analysed are modelled by means of a diagrammatic representation of its components and their interactions contributing to the system functionality.

Traditionally, the most used modelling method is the Reliability Block Diagram (RBD) which represents the components in a series of blocks connected in parallel or series configuration (Fig. 3). Each block represents a component of the system with a failure rate (λ) and a repair rate ($\mu = 1/\text{MTTR}$). Parallel paths are redundant, meaning that all of the parallel paths must fail for the parallel network to fail. By contrast, any failure along a series path causes the entire series path to fail.

Fig. 3. Complex bottom fixed tidal turbine concept - 3D Model

B. Analytical calculation

The availability of an item is given by the simplified equation (1).

$$A = \frac{\mu}{\lambda + \mu} \quad (1)$$

With:

- A being the availability of the item;
- λ being the item failure rate (i.e. the ratio of the total number of failures to the total observation time, for a stated period in the life of an item); and
- μ being the item repair rate (i.e. the inverse of the average time required to repair a failed item).

By establishing the failure and repair criteria of the system and its components, it is possible to represent the system in the form of RBD model that including the components in series, in parallel, or a combination of both. In Fig. 3, the failure of one of the components in series (A, E and F) will result in an immediate loss of the system function.

The failure of components in parallel (B, C and D) do not cause the loss of the system function unless all of them are in a failed state simultaneously.

Using this representation, it is possible to calculate the system availability using availability equations for series and parallel configurations presented below.

The availability of a group of components in a "Series configuration" is given by equation (2):

$$A_{series} = \prod_{i=1}^s A_{Component i} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- A_{series} is the resulting overall availability of a group of components in series.
- s : number of components in series;
- $A_{Component i}$: is the availability of the component "i".

And the reliability of group of component in "Parallel configuration" is given by equation (3):

$$A_{parallel} = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^p (1 - A_{Component i}) \quad (3)$$

Where:

- $A_{parallel}$ is the resulting overall availability of a group of components in parallel.
- p : number of components in parallel;
- $A_{Component i}$: is the availability of the component "i".

Using equations (1), (2) and (3), it is possible to calculate the system availability.

Therefore, the availability of system presented in Fig. 3 is calculated by:

$$A_{system} = A_{Compon.A} \cdot A_{Compon.E} \cdot A_{Compon.F} \cdot \{1 - (1 - A_{Compon.B})(1 - A_{Compon.C})(1 - A_{Compon.D})\} \quad (4)$$

$$A_{system} = \left(\frac{\mu_A}{\lambda_A + \mu_A}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_E}{\lambda_E + \mu_E}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_F}{\lambda_F + \mu_F}\right) \cdot \left\{1 - \left(1 - \frac{\mu_B}{\lambda_B + \mu_B}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\mu_C}{\lambda_C + \mu_C}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\mu_D}{\lambda_D + \mu_D}\right)\right\} \quad (5)$$

However this method is difficult to apply for extremely complex models. Using only deterministic RBD will limit the scope of the model to quantifying the impact of failure probability and repair time of the components in the turbine for the estimation of reliability or availability of the turbine. In the case of tidal turbine, there are other sources of uncertainty for system availability, such as maintenance vessel availability and suitable weather windows for maintenance operation. These two items have significant impact on the overall maintenance performance of the system, hence they need to be taken into account during the turbine RAM modelling. Therefore, considering its flexibility, Petri nets are used to develop the model. Afterwards, Monte Carlo simulations are used to evaluate the model.

Petri net is a modelling language using a directed bipartite graph that basically has four elements to be used to model the system, which are places, transitions, arcs, and tokens. The directed arcs connect places to transitions and vice versa. Places are utilized to represent state of the model component, such as failed component, good weather, or available maintenance vessel. Transitions represent instances, such as failure of component triggered by certain probability characteristics or time delay. Whereas the tokens will capture the order of the event during the simulation via transitioning between places.

Graphically places are represented as circles, while transitions as thin rectangles.

Fig. 4. Simplified depiction of Petri net model for turbine component module

Notation

P1	Turbine component in operational state
P2	Turbine component in fail state
P3	Turbine component in stand-by state
T1	Major failure occurs
T2	Minor failure occurs
T3	Maintenance takes place
T4	Turbine component to stop (when another turbine component is non operational)
T5	Turbine component restart

The flexibility of petri net enables the modelling of several types of failures for each component based on their severity or maintenance durations. In Fig. 4, it is depicted that there are two types of failures, which are major and minor failures. Consequently, the repair durations for both are different. It is also possible to model the impact of early failure detection method on the system downtime.

Petri net is also capable to model other kinds of items or events which are not pieces of equipment but that can have an influence on the system performance, such as maintenance utilities, vessel availability, spare parts or even external factors such as weather.

Fig. 5 depicts the simplified petri net model of vessel mobilization and maintenance process for minor failure that can be conducted on site for floating tidal turbine.

Some commercial petri net modelling tool can embed more logics or transition triggering mechanisms in the transitions block, hence it simplifies the model development process.

For each equipment, reliability and maintainability data are entered in the model, together with other data defined in the RAM assumptions such as logistics times, production profile, etc.

Deterministic RAM tools will convert the RAM model into complex reliability, availability formulas. The formulas can calculate several performance indicators such as the average availability of each equipment and the system itself over the system life cycle.

Notation

Fig. 5. Simplified depiction of Petri net model for vessel availability module

P1	Vessel in stand-by state
P2	Vessel ready on port
P3	Vessel arrives on the turbine location
P4	Maintenance is finished
T1	Vessel & technicians mobilisation
T2	Open weather for maintenance operation
T3	Maintenance takes place
T4	Vessel returns to port

A Monte-Carlo based tool will simulate cycles of operations over the system life cycle duration. The RAM tool will simulate equipment failures and repairing based on the probabilistic reliability data entered for each equipment.

As the tool performs the simulations, the impact of the sequence of failures and repairs on the system performance over its life cycle is progressively computed and measured.

C. Monte Carlo simulation

Monte Carlo simulations attempt to replicate or approximate real life occurrences by mathematically modelling projected events using random numbers. In practice, this means that although probabilistic distributions are being used to model the failure and repair characteristics of the components within a production system, each unique timing and sequence of events will yield different performance results.

By running a number of trial run simulations (usually called lifecycles) each based on a different random number seed and aggregating the results over all of these lifecycles, the Monte Carlo simulations can represent the overall performance of a model and the variability of that performance.

Each lifecycle has its own random number seed, which determines the timing of the events of that lifecycle. The lifecycle availabilities should be provided, together with a list of each lifecycle, its availability and the simulation seed for that lifecycle. Any given lifecycle could then be reproduced exactly by entering the random number seed, in order to analyse the series of event in this particular lifecycle.

V. Reliability Data Set

One of the most important issues in the RAM analysis process is the data used to describe the unplanned failure and subsequent repair of equipment. It is fundamental that the data is reliable and appropriate otherwise the benefits from the study will be limited.

It is important to highlight that, due to the lack of available experience on tidal turbines, most of the reliability data was collected from wind turbines reliability databases as the components and technologies are very similar.

Data for this study has been taken from the following sources in that order of priority:

- Ingeteam Historical Data:

Reliability study on wind turbine farms performed by Ingeteam that resulted in a database. A sample reliability data from this study is presented in the Fig. 6;

- Generic Wind Turbine Reliability data sources:

There are various accessible wind turbine reliability studies which can be used as surrogate data for tidal turbine reliability assessment such as: Windstats survey for Germany and Denmark, LWK and WMEP survey in Germany, and EPRI survey in USA;

- Industrial databases:

Several reliability databases are commonly used in industrial RAM studies such as OREDA 2009 [6][7] and PARLOC [8] for Offshore Oil&Gas units or I-EEE [9] for power plants.

- Generic Tidal Turbine FMEA [3]

A qualitative analysis of Tidal Turbine failures have been performed in Realtide project and was used to estimate some failure rates;

- Partner’s discussions and experience.

Fig. 6. Ingeteam reliability data sample for Wind Turbines 1500KW (relative values)

For each tidal turbine component, the failures were divided into 3 types:

- Major failures: Failure which time to repair is greater than 24 hours;
- Minor failures: failures which time to repair is between 1 hour and 24 hours;
- Trivial failures: failures which time to repair is less than 1 hour.

This categorization was essential for the modelling as trivial failures are not repaired in the same way as minor neither major failures, therefore the consequences in terms of maintenance logistics and impact on production are to be modelled differently as explained in section VI.

VI. Tidal Turbine RAM Model and assumptions

D. Base case RAM Models

Each concept was modelled considering a simple and standard tidal turbine design. It means that all typical components of each concept were represented without any redundancy; except in the case where redundancy is considered as a best practice (such as the case of mechanical seals where the benefit of its duplication is well known for turbine integrity). The fact that there is little redundancy means that almost all components would directly impact production when they fail.

For concept 3, it was considered that there are 2x50% rotors and drive trains. It means that in case of the loss of one rotor or drive train would impact 50% of production. In the case of concept 1, the failure of the rotor or the drive train will lead to total loss of production.

Generic assumptions in terms of maintenance strategy and logistics were considered. For example, maintenance on “major failures” (see definition in section V) are performed in a workshop which requires the mobilization of an Offshore Supply Vessel (OSV). Indeed, the OSV is needed to disconnect and transport the tidal turbine from sea to shore. For equipment which are accessible from the nacelle, a different maintenance logistic is required when a “trivial failure” occurs (see definition in section V). Indeed, such equipment can be repaired in loco at sea by the maintenance staff. In that case the spare parts and the maintenance staff are transported via the mobilization of a Crew Transport Vessel (CTV) and OSV is not required.

Data such as travel delays, disconnection and connection operations times and failure detection times have been defined using estimated averages according to partners experience. For example, the mobilization times of an OSV and CTV are respectively 2 weeks and 1 week. It was assumed that turbine disconnection time would be 2 days provided that weather condition is good enough during all operation, otherwise the disconnection operation has to be delayed.

Thus, meteocean data were considered in order to assess the impact on bad weather condition on maintenance operations delays and then on tidal turbine availability. However, such data are difficult to assume in a “generic”

way. So real meteocean data from the site “Passage du Fromveur” in France, where the Sabella D10 tidal turbine is being tested, was assumed in the base case. Fig. 7 provides the resume of probability of suitable weather to conduct maintenance operation based on cross-referencing the OSV required weather characteristics and Sabella D10 site historical weather data.

Fig. 7. Resume of Suitable Weather Probability for Maintenance Operation

E. Alternative cases RAM Models

After running the base case for each concept, an analysis of the critical components was performed. Then, design and monitoring recommendations were proposed and simulated in Alternative cases in order to assess their effectiveness to increase the tidal turbines availability.

Design modification should increase the reliability of the turbine (reducing the number of failures that will impact immediately the turbine). Monitoring enhancement, should predict the incipient failure and trigger maintenance activity before critical failure occurs leading to a gain of logistic time.

Each Alternative case was then compared with the base case models in order to assist in determining the options that increases the most the tidal turbines reliability and global availability.

F. Sensitivity cases RAM Models

The sensitivity cases are scenarios that are simulated and compared to each other in order to identify the robustness of the model to the variation of certain assumptions and data.

Assumption and data related to logistic times, weather conditions and failure prediction times were the ones with the most uncertainty and were the ones selected to be analysed in the sensitivity cases.

VII. RAM Results

G. Base cases

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 presents the base cases RAM results and the contribution of the most critical components to each tidal turbine concept.

a) Concept 1

Performance measured	Value
Average Production Availability (%)	71.82%
Annual Average Downtime (days/year)	102.84
Annual Average OSV Mobilisation	2.45

Fig. 8. RAM base cases results – Concept 1

The simulated availability of over 20 years of operation for the concept 1 is 71.82%. The Offshore Supply Vessel mobilisation was required 2.45 times per year for turbine’s components repair.

The most critical components are in the following order:

1. Gearbox and High Speed Shaft,
2. Power Electronic Converter,
3. Pitch System,
4. Yaw system,
5. Control System,
6. Blades, and
7. Generator.

b) Concept 3

Performance measured	Value
Average Production Availability (%)	80.09%
Annual Average Downtime (days/year)	72.68
Annual Average OSV Mobilisation	1.87
Annual Average CTV Mobilisation	1.43

Fig. 9. RAM base cases results – Concept 3

The availability of the base case over 20 years of operation for concept 3 is 80.09%. The OSV mobilisation was required 1.87 time per year and the Crew Transport Vessel mobilisation 1.43 time per year.

The most critical components are in the following order:

1. Pitch system,
2. Blades;
3. Gearbox and High Speed Shaft,
4. Power Electronic Converter,
5. Control System,
6. Low speed shaft bearings, and
7. Couplings,
8. Generator.

H. Alternative cases

Fig. 12 and Fig. 11 present the alternative cases results for each concept in terms of turbine availability, and also the average OSV and CTV mobilisations per year for each case.

a) Concept 1

Fig. 10. RAM alternative cases results – Concept1

The alternative case 1 (AC1) was defined to maximise the turbine availability. A full set of implementations were proposed as the simplification of the tidal turbine design (removal of Gearbox and High Speed Shaft, Pitch System, Yaw system), redundancy of the Power Electronic Converter and Control System, and monitoring of Blades and Generator. Consequently the resulting availability of the tidal turbine is increased to 86.03% (+14.21% of availability comparing with the base case) reducing the OSV mobilisation to 1.54 time per year.

The alternative case 2 (AC2) proposed the implementation of condition monitoring on critical components defined in the base case and demonstrated this is an effective way to prevent failure in order to increase availability. However, the Condition Monitoring strategy requires the OSV to be mobilised more frequently. The turbine availability increases 5.30% (from 71.82% in the base case to 77.13% in AC2) requiring an additional OSV mobilisation of 1.3 time per year, in average.

However, in reality a better knowledge about the turbine condition acquired with time and the number of visits/outages can be optimized when combining condition monitoring with a proper maintenance strategy leading to cost reductions. This factor was not considered in this RAM analysis limiting in the results the

effectiveness of implementing condition monitoring and also the optimisation of maintenance interventions.

Alternative case 3 (AC3) assessed the turbine availability in case condition monitoring is implemented to one individual critical component at a time. The study demonstrated that Condition Monitoring is the most efficient when applied to the most critical components which are Pitch and Gearbox (i.e. +2.01% availability for Pitch monitoring, +1.86% availability for Gearbox monitoring).

Again, OSV will be mobilised more frequently if Condition Monitoring is applied: 1 extra OSV mobilisation every 3 years in the case of Pitch monitoring.

For that reason, it is very important to define the most convenient monitoring strategy according to the criticality of the component and also to combine with optimized maintenance strategies and redesign in order to increase availability and reduce OSV mobilization.

Fig. 11. RAM alternative cases results – Concept 3

In alternative case 1 (AC1), it was suggested the simplification of the tidal turbine design (removal of Pitch system, Gearbox and High Speed Shaft), redundancy of the Power Electronic Converter and Control System, and monitoring of Blades and Generator, Low speed shaft bearings, and Couplings. The resulting availability of the tidal turbine is increased to 89.39% (+9.30% of availability comparing with the base case) reducing the mobilisation of the OSV and the CTV to 1.15 and 0.86 time per year respectively.

In alternative case 2 (AC2), the condition monitoring on critical components increases 2.44% the turbine availability (from 80.09% in the base case to 82.53% in AC2) as shown in figure 6. However, it requires the OSV and the CTV to be mobilised additionally, in average, 1.1 and 1.05 time per year respectively.

However, in reality a better knowledge about the turbine condition acquired with time and the number of visits/outages can be optimized when combining condition monitoring with a proper maintenance strategy leading to cost reductions. This factor has not been

considered in this RAM analysis limiting in the results the effectiveness of implementing condition monitoring and also the optimisation of maintenance interventions.

Alternative case 3 assesses the turbine availability in case condition monitoring is implemented to one individual critical component at a time. A specific analysis demonstrated that Condition Monitoring applied on Pitch is the most efficient to increase availability (i.e. +3.11% availability). This is because Pitch is the most critical component. However, additional OSV mobilisation are required (2 more mobilisations every 3 years) which could largely increase the OPEX. In other cases, such as for blades monitoring, while OSV mobilisation increases, the CTV mobilisation decreases.

As for concept 1, it is very important to define the most convenient monitoring strategy according to the criticality of the component and also to combine with optimized maintenance strategies and redesign in order to increase availability and reduce OSV mobilization.

I. Sensitivity cases

Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 presents the sensitivity cases RAM results and the contribution of the most critical components to each tidal turbine concept.

Fig. 12. RAM sensitivity cases results – Concept 1

a) Concept 1

The sensitivity case 1 (SC1) was carried out focusing on the impact of the weather conditions for OSV operations. The weather conditions causes up to 6.72% of unavailability, i.e. equivalent to 24.5 days/year of downtime. This is a considerable impact on the tidal turbine performance.

The sensitivity case 2 (SC2) was carried to assess the variation of availability in case the OSV is triggered when production rate is 50% or lower (instead of 100% in base case). The availability increased 1.60% in comparison with the base case while 1 additional OSV mobilisation every 10 years is required.

The sensitivity cases 3 and 4 (SC3 and SC4) focused on the OSV logistic time. The logistic time has important influence on availability and also great uncertainty. The availability range varies from 61.92% to 77.50% comparing the worst scenario (SC3 - OSV logistic time is multiplies by 2) and the best one (SC4 - OSV logistic time is divided by 2). This difference (15.58%) confirms the high influence of the OSV logistic time in the availability.

The remaining sensitivity cases (SC 5 to SC8) were carried out focusing on the failure prediction time (also called Potential to Functional Failure (P-F) interval) of critical components. Different scenarios with P-F intervals ranging from 0 to 6 months resulted in different availability from 56.66% to 76.55%. The availability increases with greater P-F interval. It was further verified that the P-F time interval caused a “mask effect” on components’ contribution to unavailability. The real impact on unavailability were so distorted that while some components had their contribution over estimated, others were under estimated. As a consequence the top critical equipment should be set up based on the scenario where the P-F interval is equal to 0.

Different scenarios with P-F intervals varying from 0 to 6 months resulted in different availability from 69.35% to 84.35%. Again, as for the concept 1, the availability increases with greater P-F interval. The same “mask effect” has been observed and so the top critical equipment should be set up based on the scenario where PF interval is equal to 0.

VIII. CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, the highlighted critical components of each concept are to be prioritized for the development of the condition monitoring system.

Comparing the results from the 2 concepts, it can be also concluded that bottom fixed turbines will be more benefited of the Condition Monitoring implementation because it helps to reduce the impact of the complexity of repairing for this concept by anticipating critical failures

The design improvement recommendations suggested in the alternative cases are to be addressed for future developments. The outcomes of the RAM study provides valuable information to the cost models about CAPEX (based on the Turbine Design structure), OPEX (based on components’ failure rates and on OSV/CTV mobilisations) and revenues (based on the turbine availability). The alternative and sensitivity cases assessed the impact of key choices such as: design structure architecture and maintenance strategies.

It is to be noted that this analysis does not take into account any preventive maintenance strategy associated with condition based maintenance that could not only enhance the tidal turbine availability but also optimise the OSV/CTV mobilisations and then OPEX.

Therefore, in an eventual cost analysis using the RAM results, it should be evaluated in economic terms the integration of the CMS in tidal turbines taking into account an effective CBM strategy based on the application of findings and developments from WP4.

It was also considered the weather conditions of a location with harsh climate location and difficult access. As the weather conditions has a significant impact on the tidal turbine availability, the results might change significantly for other locations.

One of the challenges of this study was the lack of data in the tidal turbine domain. Most of the data came from wind turbines specific databases what could lead to inconsistencies in the final result. A database specifically created for tidal turbines must be developed for further improvements. For this purpose it is also considered fundamental that tidal turbines have to be employed at real scale providing experience feedback and further developing tidal turbine technology.

Furthermore, this study may be extended to a tidal turbine farm level in order to assess and develop global O&M strategy with an optimised CAPEX/OPEX trade-off.

Finally, it is to be noted that the comparison between the 2 concepts can not be performed without an adequate cost analysis taking into consideration not only expenses from

Fig. 13. RAM sensitivity cases results – Concept 3

Sensitivity case 1 (SC1) assessed the impact of the weather conditions on OSV and CTV operations. This factor causes up to 5.55% of unavailability, i.e. equivalent to 20.26 days/year of downtime. As for concept 1, this is a considerable impact on the tidal turbine performance.

Sensitivity cases 2 and 3 (SC3 and SC4) focused on the OSV and CTV logistic times. The availability range varies from 72.24% to 84.62% comparing the worst scenario (SC2 - OSV and CTV logistic times are multiplies by 2) and the best one (SC3 - OSV and CTV logistic times divided by 2). This difference (12.38%) confirms the high influence of the OSV and CTV logistic times in the availability also for this concept.

Sensitivity cases 5 to 8 (SC5 to SC8) focused on the Potential to Functional Failure (P-F) intervals of critical

all phases of the life cycle of the turbines (CAPEX & OPEX) but also all risks related to the unavailability of the turbines.

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